

JUGGLING RESPONSIBILITIES: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY OF EARLY ADULT STUDENT-PARENTS IN BALANCING EDUCATION AND PARENTHOOD

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Juggling Responsibilities: A Multiple Case Study of Early Adult Student-Parents in Balancing Education and Parenthood

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Abstract

This qualitative research design applying multiple case study aims to explore, discover, and comprehend the journey encountered by the early adult senior high school student-parents of Dagohoy National High School, Dagohoy, Talaingod Davao del Norte. In this study, three (3) participants were chosen to participate in an in-depth interview. Thematic analysis was used in analyzing the data. This study revealed the unique characteristics of each case. From the stories of failures and moments of triumph, six (6) major themes emerged. Three (3) themes also in surviving the challenges, from the thoughts of inspiration, another three themes emerged. Because not all the respondents had a support structure, the survey's results indicated that they frequently dealt with family difficulties and concerns about managing their finances and taking care of their children. Due to their twin responsibilities, which cause them to frequently overlook the importance of their health, a relationship ranks top among their priorities, while health comes in last. This research urges the school to strengthen the conduct of guidance programs such as teenage pregnancy awareness orientation for students and responsible parenting to those student-parents to help them pursue and finish their studies and recommends Department of Education allocate a budget for the Alternative Delivery Mode teachers, a particular teacher item, that focuses only on working students, student-parents, or any similar situations that hinder the students from attending classes daily.

Keywords: *early adult senior high school student-parents, unique characteristics, failures and triumphs, surviving the challenges, thoughts of inspiration*

Introduction

Being an early adult student-parent is not a simple undertaking. Challenges such as a tough time balancing multiple tasks as a student-parent, lack of focus, mingling with classmates and peers, etc. (Cabulay, et al., 2023). Also, they frequently dread social shame, monetary troubles, and the absence of help from loved ones. In addition, early adult student-parents may have to put their educational and career goals on hold to care for their children. This can limit their opportunities and make it difficult to provide for their family. However, they also have their rewards. Young parents report that having a child gives them a sense of purpose and direction in life, and their love for their child is unparalleled (McCourt, 2018).

The study's findings in Namibia showed that it might be challenging for early-adult student parents to find adequate time to balance parenting and studying. It claims that not having enough time to study and finish projects, along with spending time with friends, partners, extended families, and children, is a major challenge for parents who are also students. They also have several difficulties in their academic careers; some report missing lectures, feeling sluggish and sleepy, and not paying attention in class because they prioritize their families (Taukeni, 2018).

Additionally, a study conducted at Northwestern University in the United States of America found that student parents frequently face financial barriers to academic performance due to their high levels of financial instability regarding housing, food, and other essentials. Because of financial barriers and real-world issues like inconsistent childcare, students with children who take out loans for postsecondary education run the risk of accruing debt without improving their chances of finding employment or being able to pay back their debts. This could lead to dropout and the loss of their credentials, which could have a detrimental effect on their future earnings (Dundar et al., 2023).

Furthermore, in the Philippines, early adult student-parents encounter difficulties juggling their two responsibilities, including bullying, time constraints, and financial difficulties (Sicam et al., 2021). Their academic achievement may be impacted by these difficulties. Additionally, 84% of the adult students in the Province of Cebu who are parents had several difficulties, including worries about their families, budgeting their costs, and finding childcare because not all of them had a support structure (Roldan et al., 2020). In Agusan del Sur, Philippines, according to research by Bustillo et al. (2024), time management is a challenge for student parents because of the frequent conflicts between their twin responsibilities of academics and fatherhood.

Moreover, early adult student-parents at Southern Philippines Agri-business and Marine and Aquatic School of Technology (SPAMAST) Digos Campus were found to be financially burdened; many of them ran out of money because they had to support both their child's education and their own. A few of them, who shared a workplace, frequently struggled to set aside money for their families' needs as well as their education. Time management was still another issue. They said it was extremely challenging since they had to develop time management skills (Torres et al., 2020).

Furthermore, this study would focus on the experiences and challenges of the early adult student-parents in the Senior High School of Dagohoy National High School. Although some studies have been conducted by Dayson et al. (2023) and Torres et al. (2020), the researchers have not come across any local studies that focus on the issues and challenges faced by the students, as stated above. Hence, this prompted the researcher to conduct this study to provide new information about the ongoing problems and the ways to overcome such challenges.

This study will become significant to the participants as their voices will be heard and give attention to addressing the challenges they have experienced. Moreover, this will also encourage the researcher for they believed that it would help them, and they would be able to gain insights and encouragement in addressing their academic battles. This would also provide relevant concepts for early adult students to continue their dreams and help them to strive for better education.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the unique characteristics of senior high school early adult student-parents in their academic battle?
2. What are the stories of failure and moments of triumph experienced by senior high school early adult student-parents in their academic battle?
3. How does each case survive the challenges they experienced in their studies?
4. What are the thoughts of inspiration that can be shared with others by each senior high school early adult student-parent in their study?

Literature Review

Early Adult Student-Parents

Students who have their own families and are still pursuing education are known as student-parents. These are the people who put their families before their education and are now making an effort to change their ways by pursuing their goals. Some of these people have been offered another chance to mend their broken dreams by their partner or family. Returning to school is a foundation for success in life and a place to start for those who are seeking education despite the obligations they have on their plate (Roldan et al., 2020).

Furthermore, early adult student-parents, however, get a source of inspiration, respect, school excuses, and important lessons in life. Their parenting experience gives them a strong personality and an inspiration to continue their educational pursuits. Though managing time is hard for them, they can surpass it through time management and parental help. Support systems such as their teachers, classmates, parents, friends, and relatives also play a significant role in their lives (Sicam et al., 2021).

On the other hand, according to the Trade Union Congress 2016, 13.9 million Filipino young students are parents. Hence, they must give up on their education to give way to the children. They must suffer the same responsibility as a student-parent in the family (Lenon et al., 2020).

Challenges of Student-Parents

Students amid early parenthood face many difficulties due to the difficulty of juggling the responsibilities of parenthood and education. Student-parents need to adjust their experience as parents and as students too. It can be difficult for them to balance parenthood and schoolwork without prioritizing one over the other. For instance, rather than concentrating solely on their studies, their behavior may contrast with their parenthood experience. It was also emphasize how difficult it is to balance being a student and a parent. They might encounter a variety of obstacles, such as negative feedback and emotional pressures (Syuraini, 2020; Visick, 2019; Springer et al., 2019).

Besides, early adult student-parents may encounter academic difficulties as a result of a lack of time, support, and resources. They might battle to stay aware of coursework, tasks, and tests while managing parental obligations. They may likewise feel disengaged and unsupported in the scholastic climate, influencing their certainty and inspiration (Ajayi et al., 2022).

Similarly, they may experience social isolation and stigma due to the perception that they are not fully committed to their children's education. This negative perception can be internalized by student-parents themselves. Due to their parental responsibilities, student-parents may not have the same opportunities to engage in extracurricular activities or socialize with other students, which can lead to social isolation (Smith & Prior, 2019).

On the other hand, Lawrence and Lee (2022) concentrate on referenced that their examination zeroed in on the experience of low-pay metropolitan youth offsetting nurturing with their schooling. The scientists found that understudy guardians confronted a few difficulties battling — with nurturing liabilities with the disgrace related with being a youthful parent. The concentrate additionally distinguishes a few factors that assisted these understudies with succeeding, including support from loved ones, admittance to assets like guiding and coaching, and school strategies that obliged their nurturing liabilities.

Furthermore, as student-parents move along their academic path, there are obstacles. These incorporate requests or obligations, social

and self-assumption which prevent their advancement in examinations. Thus, student-parent juggles include self-neglect, financial difficulties, social stigma, and competing demands. These are likely to make it difficult for them to prioritize their priorities. Additionally, gender issues, childcare constraints, a lack of self-belief, and unresponsive institutions were identified as obstacles for them in some studies (Grenier & Burke, 2018; Cabaguing, 2017; Moghadam et al., 2017).

Moreover, student-parents face the inability to effectively manage their time with their children, partners, families, and friends, as well as their studies, which is yet another obstacle they face. They convey a weighty job in studentship and being engaged with early life as a parent builds the difficulty they experience. To fulfill their dual duties, they had to divide their time. Additionally, the diverse culture of motherhood forces them to give up one role in favor of another. It may force student mothers to assume one role over another. (Lidgard, 2018, Taukeni, 2019, Zhang, 2021).

In conclusion, early adult student parents face several obstacles that can hinder their children's academic success and happiness. It is fundamental to perceive and address these difficulties by giving monetary help. Thusly, understudy guardians can defeat difficulties and accomplish instructive objectives.

Coping Mechanisms of Early Adult Student-Parents

Student-parents received better support and more appropriate access to the offered support. of local area could increment. Having a sense of community and belonging is indeed vital to both psychological well-being and understudy accomplishment for understudies who are likewise guardians. The young student-parent population can more fully immerse in their academic experience when feeling supported and understood when they feel they belong and know they are part of a learning community (Scharp et al., 2021).

Additionally, the impact of inspiration on the academic motivation and self-efficacy of student-parents. It was found that openness to fruitful good examples who had made instructive progress while nurturing propelled student-parents and decidedly impacted their inspiration. Inspired student-parents demonstrated higher self-efficacy and perseverance in their academic pursuits (Lekli & Kaloti, 2015).

Furthermore, extraordinary requirements of young student-parents in schools and gave suggestions to teachers to help their prosperity. It features the significance of educator compassion, adaptability, and coordinated effort with parents to establish a strong and comprehensive instructive climate. It was also mentioned that teaching empathy is important because it requires comprehending and responding to the various needs and feelings of students. By exhibiting sympathy, teachers lay out a protected and steady space where young student-parents feel esteemed and understood. Equally important is adaptability, which enables educators to modify their teaching strategies, resources, and assessments to accommodate various learning styles and individual strengths (Pelletier & Dunbar, 2021).

Moreover, effective proper time management is essential for student-parents. Scheduling focused study time and keeping deadlines enables kids to achieve academically. Stress is reduced, and a routine is provided by good time management. By prioritizing activities and removing distractions, it improves productivity (Cabulay et al., 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

Qualitative research is used to investigate the root causes of possible issues. It can also mean research techniques that explore the observations, experiences, feelings, and thoughts of participants to produce a practice, narrative, or descriptive account (Stake, 2010). Also, when researchers aim to gather data based on human perceptions and understanding, qualitative methodology is most helpful. Inquiries and procedures, participant data collection, and data analysis are all part of the process of examining and comprehending the people or groups assigned to a social human problem (Creswell, 2013).

In this study, the researchers investigate multiple factors with extended engagement, in-depth interviews, and data-gathering procedures to explore, probe, and understand the experiences, challenges, causes, and insights of the senior high school early adult student-parents. They do this using a qualitative design. Furthermore, this design is appropriate for use because it helps to comprehend the challenges that early adult student parents in senior high school face in their academic endeavors as well as their experiences and personal circumstances.

Moreover, in this study, a multiple-case methodology was applied. Since it examines real life through extensive, in-depth data collection and multiple bounded systems over time, involving a wide range of evidence sources and report case themes and case descriptions, it is a suitable methodology (Creswell, 2013). Like this, a multiple case study approach to research comprises employing multiple sources of evidence to conduct an empirical investigation of a modern phenomenon within its real-life context. When there is a blurring of the lines between the phenomenon and context, it becomes even more valuable. When the case studies are compared, the researcher can bring a significant amount of influence to the literature through the contrasts and similarities (Yin, 2009).

The researchers used a variety of sources of evidence from the selected participants to collect the unseen viewpoints and perspectives of senior high school early adult student-parents regarding their experiences, difficulties, and insights. This type of research is known

as multiple case study research. Four research questions were the center of an in-depth interview that aimed to produce thorough descriptions of this study, considering the participants' experiences and points of view. The interview aided in gaining an understanding of the early adult student-parents perspectives regarding their experiences as early adult student-parents in senior high school.

Participants

There are at least three (3) participants in this multiple-case study qualitative research project. Therefore, in this study, Dagohoy National High School early adult student-parents were three (3) senior high school students. A multiple case study includes three (3) to four (4) different cases for comparison, as stated by Patton (2002).

The researchers chose to use purposive sampling in this study. A method called "purposeful sampling" is employed to extract rich data from participants who have been chosen based on their willingness to share their experiences with the researcher (Polkinghorne, 2005). Using purposive sampling, the pre-inclusion criteria in selecting participants were as follows; (1) the participant must be enrolled at Dagohoy National High School in the School Year (2022-2023). (2) they must be senior high school students. (3) they must be aged 20 to 39, and (4) they must be student-parents. The criteria for selecting the participants included male and female students with different experiences and challenges as senior high school early adult student-parents.

The interviewees in qualitative research were apprised of the interview procedure and the location and time of the interview. Ensuring the complete confidentiality of each participant was the primary objective (Fossheim & Ingierd, 2015). The selected participants provided informed consent that included the reason for the interview and its date and time.

Furthermore, the researchers requested permission to record the entire interview to gather data from the chosen participants for this study. In addition, they requested a system that would guarantee that the data, particularly the printed and electronic ones, were stored and would allow for their retention, storage, and eventual disposal after the designated storage period had elapsed. The three early-adult senior high school student-parent participants were given pseudonyms to protect study confidentiality.

The first case is the Married Student-Mother who is carrying a child in her womb. She is living with her husband together with their two (2) daughters in Barangay Dagohoy, Talaingod, Davao del Norte. She is 26 years old and a grade 12 student at Dagohoy National High School.

The second case is the Married Student-Father living with his pregnant wife and two kids in Barangay Dagohoy Talaingod, Davao del Norte. He is 29 years old and currently a senior high school student at Dagohoy National High School.

In the third case, is a Single Student-Mother. She is 22 years old and lives in Barangay Dagohoy Talaingod, Davao del Norte. To afford her studies and support her son, she chooses to be a working student. She is now in 11th Grade at Dagohoy National High School.

Instruments

Observations, interviews, and documents were among the various methods of data collection employed by qualitative researchers. Through in-depth interviews, the experiences and observations of the participants served as the foundation for this study (Creswell, 2007). Also, in-depth interviews were the most popular method of gathering data because they allowed the interviewer to get information straight from the subject. This method worked well for obtaining highly personalized data as well as for deciphering and comprehending the motivations, attitudes, feelings, and beliefs that participants were hiding about a given topic (Austin, 2015).

During the in-depth interview, participants in this study were asked whether they felt comfortable using the language they had selected. To elicit from the participants more in-depth and coherent ideas and thoughts, the researchers asked follow-up questions which were not included in the interview guide. The opportunity for participants to share their perspectives and experiences on the subject was greatly aided by an in-depth interview.

Moreover, observation protocols were carried out to produce a largely uncontested description and help gather first-hand information (Morgan et al., 2016). The participants in this study were enrolled in Dagohoy National High School, located in Dagohoy Talaingod, Davao del Norte, which served as the study's setting for primary data sources. For the academic year 2022–2023, the researchers ran the study from April 2023 to May 2023. The selected senior high school early adult student-parents at the institution were interviewed. Additionally, it allowed them to gather data for creating vicarious experiences that would benefit the reader. Additionally, the selected participants were observed multiple times.

To support the findings of this study, researchers employed secondary sources in this regard. Secondary sources offer first-hand data and insights from fellow scholars. Primary sources are described, interpreted, or synthesized. To bolster the information, she provided to the selected participants, the researcher in this study used books, journals, and secondary sources that she read online. The information obtained from the selected participants was reinforced with the aid of secondary sources (Streefkerk 2018).

Procedure

The researchers took rigorous steps in the collection of data. They also engaged in a series of events to collect data before arriving after the study. Creswell (2007) supported the idea that the qualitative researcher tied up a series of events in the collecting data. A vital

step was to find participants involved in this research, the convenience and accessibility of materials, and the place to conduct the study to obtain accurate information.

This study was reviewed by a panel of experts. After this, the researchers sent permission to Dagohoy National High School's administrator, where the participants are currently studying. After the approval, each participant from the school was provided with a letter of consent to inform them about the purpose of the study and ask them to affix their signature before the interview.

Additionally, participants' availability and convenience were taken into consideration when setting schedules; however, this was done one participant at a time. An extensive interview with senior high school early adult student-parents was one of the methods used to gather data for this study. To conduct the in-depth interviews, the researchers gave them an interview protocol. They recorded the interview to collect data, and they later transcribed the outcome. Also, they took notes to capture the main points that the participants shared during the interview, which was recorded verbatim using an audio recorder, after obtaining the participants' consent to record all their responses. Notably, the researchers continued to ask pertinent follow-up questions about the selected subject until the saturation point was reached, thereby enriching the data. The data collected from the informants was then transcribed.

Furthermore, gathering data for transcription is a laborious process that calls for a great deal of patience and persistence. It is essential to the data analysis process, which forms the foundation for the main themes of the study. The analyst and research adviser verified, examined, and studied the information gleaned from the transcription.

Data Analysis

The focus of this multiple-case study was data analysis. The data was collected, recorded, and transcribed by researchers, who also used methods to carefully assess the information. The data collected for this multiple case study was analyzed using coding, thematic analysis, cross-case analysis, and the formulation of significant themes.

Besides, coding was used in the data analysis process after all research interviews had been transcribed and verified. As mentioned, coding is the process of identifying the themes, problems, and distinctions that the participant narratives disclose. This will lead to improvements in the themes (Sutton, 2015).

In addition, the process of coding in this study involved carefully labeling, underlining, and marking the pertinent and intriguing ideas that emerged from the participants' answers. Subsequently, the investigators collected all the information into code-designated groups. These codes gave the researcher insight into the recurring themes and shared interpretations within the data. Following a comprehensive data interpretation process, the researchers recorded additional passages and found themes that connected the text. This allowed the researchers to index the text into categories, draw conclusions, and create a framework of related thematic ideas.

Moreover, the theme of thematic analysis was defined as the process of characterizing and locating both explicit and implicit ideas in the data. Assarroudi et al. (2018) cited Hsieh and Shannon (2005), who stated that codes were generally created to represent the identified themes, and raw data were applied as summary markers for subsequent analysis. Furthermore, using thematic analysis, one can methodically learn about and develop empathy for an individual, a group, an organization, an interaction, a situation, or a phenomenon by analyzing qualitative data (Guest et al., 2016). In this study, through a methodical approach to interpreting and analyzing the gathered data, the investigator made sure of this by carefully identifying potential themes or ideas like other data used to develop more fixed and succinct conclusions.

Additionally, another method of bringing the diverse data from participant responses together inductively before the study's theoretical understanding is to formulate major themes. According to Vasileiou et al. (2018), the potential themes are determined by the phenomena or characteristics under study, the preexisting professional definition found in the literature review, the values of the researchers—including their theoretical orientation and personal experience—as well as local, commonsense constructs. To find potential themes that were essential to the phenomenon being studied, the researchers carefully reread and examined pertinent phrases in the context of this study. Additionally, the researchers gave us their word that there were no biases and that their fair intentions were the reason behind the theme's fair formulation.

Ethical Considerations

The Belmont Report (1974) made an effort to enumerate the fundamental ideas that the Commission had determined during its discussion. The three fundamental values of beneficence, justice, and respect for persons that are acknowledged in our customary practice will apply to research ethics involving human subjects (Podany, 2017).

The purpose of this study was to investigate, identify, and comprehend the difficulties faced by early adult student-parents in senior high school, as well as the reasons behind these difficulties and the strategies used by the participants to overcome them. Given their backgrounds, settings, and sensitivity to the subject matter, the researcher must ensure the safety and complete protection of the participants, who would be deemed vulnerable in this study. Thus, the fundamental ideas that serve as the generally acknowledged foundation for research ethics were emphasized in the Belmont Report (1974). These are respect for person, beneficence, and justice.

The first principle, respect for a person, pertains to the investigator's courtesy towards the participants and their rights and autonomous decision to take part in this research. Participants must be regarded independently as individuals who decide for themselves what

general goals to pursue, act on those decisions, and learn how to keep themselves safe. To follow this rule and recognize that all the research subjects who were chosen are young adults (Creswell, 2007).

In the context of this study. The researchers sent an informed consent form to the senior high school early adult student-parents asking and signing their permission to participate in the study actively and willingly. As such, the researchers made sure to respect participants, asking them if they genuinely desired to be part of this research as informants. Furthermore, when they reached the agreement, researchers encouraged them to read and sign the informed consent signifying their willingness to participate in this study. From there, the researcher prepared and set the interview schedule at a convenient time for both.

They were advised of their rights as study participants by the researchers before the interview as part of their permission. They had a right to have their identities protected during this project; to maintain the confidentiality of their answers and their identity through anonymity, the researchers coded the in-depth interview. Additionally, individuals were granted the freedom to ask questions before, during, and after the interview as well as the complete right to withdraw and decline to participate in the study at any time they felt uncomfortable doing so.

Similarly, to collect all their comments, the researchers requested permission in advance to record the whole interview. Eventually, the researchers began the interview after obtaining their consent. Only the experiences of senior high school early adult student-parents were the subject of the interview questions, and researchers got in touch with them to review the transcripts of their interviews. Furthermore, if they see any written replies that are incorrect, they are free to add, remove, or alter part of the responses.

The second principle is beneficence, which refers to making efforts to secure the well-being of the research participants and minimize harm. Benefits from research might include making friends with other participants, learning new things via involvement, or having the chance to improve society or win people's respect (Creswell, 2007).

In this research, the researchers would ensure that the research participants would find the findings valuable, advantageous, and helpful. In addition to their selected participants, other students who have experienced similar things will find value in the study's findings, which will motivate them to put in their best effort in their coursework. Throughout the course of the research study, the investigators ensured that the objectives of the study were met with the greatest possible benefit and the least amount of potential risk to the informants.

Through sharing their thoughts and issues with the subject, the study assisted them in lessening the load that participants may have felt. As early adult student-parents in senior high school, the researchers would allow them to speak for themselves and address issues and concerns about their successes and setbacks. The purpose of this study was to strengthen the participants' willpower and motivation to continue their education despite the obstacles they faced along the way.

In this report, since it is their responsibility as the investigators to protect participant confidentiality and the identities of the participating institutions, the researchers took care to ensure that no information that could be used to identify the participants was included. Instead, they gave each participant a pseudonym and took responsibility for their safety and well-being. Additionally, after receiving approval to conduct the study, the researchers took the convenience of the informants into account when scheduling the study's conduct. They also took into account the request of the selected informants to reschedule the interview date and time.

Lastly, the ethical principle of justice requires a reasonable allocation of the risk and benefits as a finding of the investigators. People must be equally exposed to the benefits and risks of the study regardless of their gender, ethnicity, race, or any other classification, and they can only be included or excluded for reasons related to the research questions (Scott, 2018). For the research to be successful, the participants' contributions must be recognized for their best efforts (Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). To ensure justice, the researcher also sent copies of the research to the school where the study was conducted.

The investigator and the study site must take into account reasonable and equitable terms of recruitment when selecting informants in order to uphold the ethical principle of justice in this study. Additionally, the needs of the researchers would come before the goals of the study. The researcher's questions to the research participants had to be pertinent and important to the investigation. The investigators ensured that the informants were suitably accommodated, and they should be duly acknowledged for their time and hard work. Add to the adherence of Belmont's report that this study conforms to Republic Act No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data Privacy Act (DPA), which aims to reconcile the privacy of rights with the efficient utilization of information. Under the policy statement of the Act, it is understood that even the law guarantees the protection of an individual's fundamental right to privacy. The free flow of information for growth, national development, and innovation must also be ensured by the investigator. The DPA, while upholding the data—a person's rights whose personal information is collected, stored, and processed- does not impede access to information, which may hinder progress and advancement. It does not impede the processing of personal data for research. The act supports information freedom, initiatives for data sharing, and the responsible use and processing of personal data.

In this study, To improve data processing security, the researchers ensured that informants' privacy and anonymity were preserved wherever feasible. To prevent the identities of the selected informants from being discovered, they made sure code names were used. It is imperative that the gathered data be appropriately managed, utilized, and stored in a locked cabinet that can only be accessed by those with authorization. Furthermore, the information gathered from the selected informants would only be accessible to the

researcher, adviser, and expert panel.

Results and Discussion

Cross Case Analysis

Presented here is the cross-case analysis of each case. The cases have similarities that were given accounts to give further details on the study. This is based on the results and interpretations of each participant. It corresponds with the four major questions of the study. This part also contains subheadings that cover: the unique characteristics of each case as described by the senior high school early adult student parents; the stories of failures and moments of triumph they experienced; the ways of surviving the challenges faced by them; and the thoughts of inspiration they shared with others.

Profile of Senior High School Early Adult Student-Parents

Presented the profile of each case as described by the senior high school early adult student parents. The 25-year-old married student-mother is enrolled in grade 12 at Dagohoy National High School in Dagohoy, Talaingod, Davao del Norte, as indicated by the table. She is married and has two children and is now expecting her third. The married student-father is 29 years old and enrolled in the previously mentioned school. The student in the second scenario is also in grade 12. He claims to be married to his expectant wife and to have two kids. Lastly, the third case is that of the 22-year-old single mother who is enrolled in Grade 11 at the aforementioned school. She claims that she reared her child by herself.

Table 1. *Profile of Each Case*

	<i>The Married Student-Mother</i>	<i>The Married Student-Father</i>	<i>The Single-Student Mother</i>
Age	25	29	22
Grade Level	Grade 12	Grade 12	Grade 11
Status	Married Mother	Married Father	Single Mother

Accounts of the Individual Characteristics

Presented in this table of this study are the accounts of the unique individual characteristics of each case. It was vital for the researchers to know the unique characteristics of each case. It included individual personalities and attitudes. The married student-mother comes first. She characterizes herself as inspired, citing her family as the primary source of inspiration. For this reason, she persists in her studies in spite of obstacles related to both her family and her education. She added that her husband encourages her to pursue her education and is a huge supporter of her.

Furthermore, the second case is the Married Student-Father. He also sees himself as an inspired father because of his wife and children. He believes that once he finishes his education, he will be able to provide for his family. He also describes himself as responsible because he honors his commitments to his family and his education. Occasionally, he was running behind schedule at school because of family obligations. Finally, the third case is Single-Student Mother. She considers herself to be thoughtful because she keeps studying for her son as well as for herself. She is also resourceful in that she is taking this action solely to support her son's needs and her education. Lastly, her informant describes her as a goal-oriented mother who also pursues her studies. She aspires to complete her education and provide a good life for her son.

Table 2. *Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Unique Characteristics of Each Case*

<i>Cases</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
The Married Student-Mother	The Inspired Student-Mother	My inspiration comes from my spouse and child, which is why I returned to school. I must keep going to school so that my kids won't grow up to be like me.
	The Unique Student	Although my classmates are still young and single, I am a mother of two children, and we are expecting another child. This makes me different from them.
	Student-Mother Having Supportive Husband	My spouse is encouraging of my academic endeavors. He still motivates me to finish my education for the benefit of our family, even in the face of life's challenges.
The Married Student-Father	The Inspired Student-Father	My spouse and kids are the reasons I want to continue my education. This is the reason I decided to go back to school. I want to live up to my dreams and support them in the future, which is why I want to do so. I might be able to support them after I graduate from college if I land a good job that pays well.
	A Father with Great Sense of Responsibility	My classmates are still single, so we have different responsibilities in life, but I am different because I am already a parent. Given that I am a father and am responsible for providing for my family, I feel a stronger sense of duty than other students who are single and have different priorities.
	The Matured Student-Father	As I continued my education, I grew older than my classmates and proved to be a more mature person than they were. I also used to chastise them by emphasizing the positive actions they should take and cautioning them against the bad ones.
The Single Student-Mother	The Thoughtful Mother	As a mother and student, I consider my child's future frequently. I'm going to keep going to school so that I can support my child and give him the best things he deserves.

Mother	The Clever Mother	I make a real effort to find ways to further my education in addition to being a mother and student. I make every effort to support both my child's and my own education.
	The Goal-Oriented Mother	She intends to finish her education. She applied to be a working student to support her son and her education because she hopes to have a stable job in the future (INF01)

Cross Case Analysis on the Stories of Failures and Moments of Triumphs of Each Case

Presented in this table are the accounts of the stories of failures and moments of triumph in each case. Bringing together the responses of the participants in all cases, the researchers have come up with the following themes which are common to some: experienced lack of focus in studies; monetary challenges; facing difficulties in school tasks and family were the themes from failures. On the other hand, becoming optimistic in every situation; surviving the trials in the study; and becoming inspired to continue studies were themes from their moments of triumph.

Table 3. Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Stories of Failures and Moments of Triumph of Each Case

Themes	Cases		
	1	2	3
Experienced Lack of Focus in Studies	√	√	√
Monetary Challenges	√	√	√
Facing Difficulties in School Tasks and Family	√	√	
Being Discriminated by Others			√
Being Worried about the Situation			√
Setting Limitations Because of the Priorities			√
Becoming Optimistic in Every Situation	√		√
Surviving the Trials in Study	√	√	√
Becoming Inspired to Continue Studies		√	√
Become a Responsible Mother	√		
Reaching the Lifetime Dream		√	

Cross Case Analysis on Surviving the Challenges of Senior High School Early Adult Student-Parents

This table presented the cross-case analysis on surviving the challenges of senior high school early adult student parents. Considering all the participants' responses in all cases, the researchers have come up with the following themes, which are common to the two, if not all 3 cases: making ways to address financial problems; asking assistance from others; and having faith in God.

Table 4. Major Themes and Core Ideas on Surviving the Challenges of Each Case

Themes	Cases		
	1	2	3
Making Ways to Address Financial Problems	√	√	√
Asking for Assistance from Others	√	√	√
Having Faith in God		√	√
Being Cheered Up by Loved Ones	√		
Being Persistent in School Tasks and Family		√	
Striving Hard to Attend Classes		√	
Learning from Failures			√
Making Study as Priority			√

Cross Case Analysis on the Thought of Inspiration of Senior High School Early Adult Student-Parents

The cross-case analysis of the accounts of the thoughts of inspiration for each case. After compiling all the participant responses from each of the three cases, the researchers identified the following themes that were present in at least two of the cases: be goal-oriented, always ask for guidance from the teachers, be thankful for others, and be faithful to God.

Table 5. Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Thoughts of Inspiration of Each Case

Themes	Cases		
	1	2	3
Be Goal-Oriented	√		√
Always Ask for Guidance from the Teachers	√	√	
Be Thankful to Others	√		√
Be Faithful to God		√	√
Be Courageous		√	
Have Eagerness to Achieve One's Goals		√	
Hoping for the Teacher's Continuous Assistance		√	

Unique Characteristics of Senior High School Early Adult Student-Parents

From the data gathered through the interviews with the five cases, the researchers discovered their unique characteristics.

The Married Student-Mother referred to herself as inspired, noting that her family motivates her to pursue her education. She is special because her spouse is incredibly encouraging. Additionally, The Married Student-Father says that his family inspires him to complete schoolwork. In addition, he behaves responsibly and maturely around his peers. Finally, The Single Student-Mother characterizes herself as a goal-oriented, astute, and considerate student-mother.

Stories of Failures and Moments of Triumph of Senior High School Early Adult Student-Parents

In this part, stories of failures and moments of triumph of senior high school early adult student-parents are discussed. From the interview, the information gathered produced the following themes: (1) experiencing a lack of focus in studies; (2) monetary challenges; (3) facing difficulties in school tasks and family; (4) becoming optimistic in every situation; (5) survived the trials in the study; and (6) become inspired to continue studies.

Experienced Lack of Focus in Studies

For instance, when early adult experience parenthood, their behavior may contrast with this, instead of focusing all their attention on studies (Visick, 2009). In the study of Manalang (2012), practical problems faced by student-parents are evident, such as difficulty in managing; time efficiently, including a lack of time to study, skipping classes, and being unable to complete academic requirements because of their babies which result in a lack of focus in their studies. In cases where student mothers have children, their obligation to scaffold their children is also why they have difficulty meeting their academic demands. On the other hand, some also describe skipping class lectures because they cannot focus, they feel weak and drowsy from being hands-on parents. Comparatively, a study also showed that student mothers experienced difficulties in taking care of their children, especially when sick. It disturbs their focus and attention, which significantly affects their studies.

Monetary Challenges

Facing problems, particularly in monetary matters can truly negatively impact the mental and physical health of a person. It is also indicated that stress and pressure levels for people who have money problems along with severe stress and even some depressive symptoms, can affect their performance. Being a parent while pursuing studies also poses certain risks, as the responsibility of being a parent requires financial stability (Maisela & Ross, 2018). Furthermore, financial problems were considered one of the problems being confronted by student-parents. Those financially unstable, have trouble budgeting their money for school expenses and their child's basic needs, and their daily expenses, even those who have partners to support them (Esperitu et al., 2023).

Facing Difficulties in School Tasks and Family

Students who are involved in early parenthood are facing various challenges as these dual roles (parenting and schooling) are not an easy task (Syuraini, 2020). Early adult student-parents need to balance their time between taking care of the children and making time for schoolwork or school activities as well. Combining parenthood and studying without settling the activities over the other is a great dilemma for student-parents. Being in parenthood while studying is such a challenging role. They might face different barriers, including emotional pressures and negative feedback from others (Springer et al., 2009).

Becoming Optimistic in Every Situation

Positive people are happier because they imagine affirmative events more vividly and expect them to occur sooner. This all boosts the luscious feeling of anticipation, which is greater the more pleasurable the anticipated event, the more vividly we can imagine it, the more probable we think it is to happen, and the sooner it will happen. Of course, it makes sense that having a sense of hope and a positive attitude about the future would make us more content in the present (Seligman, 2018).

Additionally, according to Dollar (2021) having a positive mindset in every situation is scientifically proven to boost happiness and motivate people to achieve goals. Student-parents who actively work to recognize the positive aspects of their life naturally start to see silver linings in challenging situations. The results showed that students must always think positively despite the failures encountered during the process because those failures will help them as they continue their tasks.

Survived the Trials in Study

According to Saldaña (2014), surviving trials is important because it helps someone learn and grow. Trials often involve challenges or difficult situations that test your abilities and knowledge. By surviving these trials, you gain valuable experience, develop problem-solving skills, and build resilience. It prepares you for future endeavors and enhances your overall educational journey.

Become Inspired to Continue Studies

The student's parents, however, get the source of inspiration, respect, school excuses, and important life lessons. Their parenting

experience gives them a strong personality and an inspiration to continue their educational pursuits. Though managing time is hard for them, they can surpass it through time management and parental help (Sicam, 2021).

Surviving the Challenges of Senior High School Early Adult Student-Parents

In this part, the coping mechanism of each case. Coming from the interview, the information gathered produced the following themes: (1) making ways to address financial problems, (2) asking for assistance from others, and (3) having faith in God.

Making Ways to Address Financial Problems

Grable and Joo (1999) summarized the coping strategies related to financial problems, which include reducing expenses, finding work, borrowing money, and seeking help. They considered help-seeking behavior a coping strategy utilized in response to financial problems. The financial help-seeking process can be divided into five stages: exhibiting financial behaviors, evaluating one's financial behaviors, identifying the causes of those financial behaviors, deciding to seek help, and choosing among available assistance options.

Additionally, addressing students' funding challenges as early as possible would mitigate the burden and stress of students trying to secure financial aid while also trying to cope with their academic and other commitments. These include finding a part-time job and addressing personal issues such as accommodation, food, and living expenses (Pather, 2015).

Asking for Assistance from Others

According to Page (2019), asking for help from others allows us to surround ourselves with people who can make us feel good and facilitate further development. These people create optimism and hope that we can deal with challenging situations, which improves our resilience. If we can ask for help and obtain feedback, we can overcome setbacks and grow. Furthermore, the research found that high-performing Students are more likely to seek advice from their colleagues, mentors, and higher-ups. This may be because high performers want to improve and, as such, seek advice to identify and improve their weaknesses.

Besides, Ribiero (2020) stated that collaboration improves the way a team works together and solves problems. This leads to more innovation, efficient processes, increased success, and improved communication. A team reaches a common goal through a combination of individual and team-driven efforts. With a clear goal in mind, you understand your role and the purpose of your work. This means you can combine your abilities and knowledge to improve your workflow and achieve your common goal. Aligning these goals leads to team-wide support, contributing to all-around skill sharing and increased productivity.

Having Faith in God

According to Baldacchino et al. (2012), praying is an instrument of strengthening the individual's connection to God as a source of strength and hope, while at the same time strengthening the individual in everyday life. By having faith in God, challenges that come our way will be easier to overcome and will shape the way individuals live.

Thought of Inspiration of Senior High School Early Adult Student-Parents

Through this study, the researchers were able to discover the thoughts of inspirations behind each case. The following themes emerged acquired from the interview results: (1) be goal-oriented; (2) always ask for guidance from the teachers; (3) be thankful to others; and (4) be faithful to God.

Be Goal-Oriented

Being goal-oriented means that you set objectives for yourself and dedicate time and energy to meeting them. You should have goals for the short term (shorter than a year) and the long term (longer than a year) that concern your academic, professional, and personal lives. However, it is important that your goals are attainable and that you have thought through how you are going to accomplish them (Dockree et al., (2019).

Always Ask for Guidance from the Teachers

Guiding students is one of the most important facets of a teacher's job. Supporting them as they work through important decisions can ensure that they choose the path in life that's right for them. In a low-income, multicultural urban school, students often face a variety of hurdles, including poverty, parental neglect, violence, housing issues, language difficulties, and immigration. They often need guidance to help them see that there's always hope for their future (Barlie 2022).

Be Thankful to Others

As a trait, an individual practices gratitude as part of their daily life, and it is considered a character strength. It is important to remember that gratitude is a strength that can be enhanced with awareness and practice. It is also important to acknowledge and be thankful for the help of other people (McCullough et al.,2002). In addition, it has been learned that gratitude helps people focus on the positive aspects of their lives. Gratitude can help build and maintain relationships with others, resulting in hope, life satisfaction, and more proactive behaviors toward others (Passmore & Oades, 2016).

Be Faithful to God

Faith in God can be a source of inspiration and support, empowering individuals to overcome challenges and find purpose in their journey. Additionally, being faithful to God as a student-parent provides strength, guidance, and hope. It offers resilience during difficult times, helps in decision-making, instills values, and fosters a sense of community (Konyo, 2023). Additionally, according to Martinez (2022), trusting in God helps us find meaning and purpose in life, seek guidance during challenging times, and have faith in something greater than ourselves. It provides solace and a sense of peace in uncertain circumstances.

Conclusions

The interviews with the participants helped the researchers a lot in understanding the varying experiences and views regarding the phenomenon of senior high school early adult student-parents. Hence, it is now time to use understanding to provide wisdom and enlightenment on how the challenges of the said students can be addressed. In this section, discussions are divided among the persons or entities that may find this study beneficial in the future.

First, for the senior high school early adult student-parents, the study has produced rich implications that may help them cope and survive in their learning process. The study found that the challenges they experienced in their studies made them stronger and more motivated to continue their studies despite the hardships they faced. They must strengthen their motivation to continue what they have started to achieve their dreams.

Furthermore, teachers must strengthen their passion and motivation in teaching and understanding the early adult student-parents. Their understanding would be a great help to the said students to continue and finish their studies. They would also suggest a program to the school administrators and DepEd officials about how to help the said students pursue their studies without any biases.

On the other hand, the school must require an intensification of the guidance program such as teenage pregnancy awareness orientation for students and responsible parenting to those student-parents to help them pursue and finish their studies before building their own families. Educational information concerning the situations of being student-parents must be given to the young learners, and a follow-up information drive must be conducted for all the students. With these activities, students will always be reminded of the challenges they may face as student-parents.

Moreover, government entities, specifically the Department of Social Welfare and Development and Department of Education advocating for financial assistance, and targeted seminars on time management for senior high school early adult student-parents, thereby offering practical support to enhance their academic journey. These conclusions present a comprehensive perspective that contributes to the ongoing discourse on the challenges and support mechanisms essential for the success of student-parents in their studies.

This study explores the experiences of senior high school early adult student-parents in their academic battle. However, this qualitative investigation is limited only to the experiences of three (3) selected students at Dagohoy National High School, Dagohoy, Talaingod, Davao del Norte.

Since the study is based on the insights, stories, and experiences of senior high school early adult student-parents, the implications suggest that further research should be conducted to validate all the claims and responses of the participants by using a larger sample size or a more significant number of research participants.

Moreover, because this study focuses on Dagohoy National High School only, further research should be done on other schools where numerous early adult students are continuing to study. On the other hand, further research can also be addressed to provide solutions to the difficulties experienced by the said students in their studies. In this way, it will help them overcome the barriers that hinder them from attaining self-actualization and validation for the victory they have accomplished.

Lastly, since the findings of this study were viewed through the lens of the student-parents, research may be conducted with the teachers who have a direct relationship with the stated students to triangulate the claims of this inquiry further.

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